

INTEGERS WITH A LARGE SMOOTH DIVISOR

William D. Banks

Department of Mathematics, University of Missouri, Columbia, MO 65211, USA
bbanks@math.missouri.edu

Igor E. Shparlinski

Department of Computing, Macquarie University, Sydney, NSW 2109, Australia
igor@ics.mq.edu.au

Received: 7/19/06, Revised: 1/31/07, Accepted: 2/2/07, Published: 4/3/07

Abstract

We study the function $\Theta(x, y, z)$ that counts the number of positive integers $n \leq x$ which have a divisor $d > z$ with the property that $p \leq y$ for every prime p dividing d . We also indicate some cryptographic applications of our results.

1. Introduction

For every integer $n \geq 2$, let $P^+(n)$ and $P^-(n)$ denote the largest and the smallest prime factor of n , respectively, and put $P^+(1) = 1$, $P^-(1) = \infty$. For real numbers $x, y \geq 1$, let $\Psi(x, y)$ and $\Phi(x, y)$ denote the counting functions of the sets of *y-smooth numbers* and *y-rough numbers*, respectively; that is,

$$\Psi(x, y) = \#\{n \leq x : P^+(n) \leq y\} \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi(x, y) = \#\{n \leq x : P^-(n) > y\}.$$

For a very wide range in the xy -plane, it is known that

$$\Psi(x, y) \sim \varrho(u) x \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi(x, y) \sim \omega(u) \frac{x}{\log y},$$

where u denotes the ratio $(\log x)/\log y$, $\varrho(u)$ is the *Dickman function*, and $\omega(u)$ is the *Buchstab function*; the definitions and certain analytic properties of $\varrho(u)$ and $\omega(u)$ are reviewed in Sections 2 and 3 below.

In this paper, our principal object of study is the function $\Theta(x, y, z)$ that counts positive integers $n \leq x$ for which there exists a divisor $d \mid n$ with $d > z$ and $P^+(d) \leq y$; in other words,

$$\Theta(x, y, z) = \#\{n \leq x : n_y > z\},$$

where n_y denotes the largest y -smooth divisor of n . The function $\Theta(x, y, z)$ has been previously studied in the literature; see [1, 6, 7, 8].

For x, y, z varying over a wide domain, we derive the first two terms of the asymptotic expansion of $\Theta(x, y, z)$. We show that the main term can be naturally defined in terms of the *partial convolution* $\mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v)$ of ϱ with ω , which is defined by

$$\mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v) = \int_v^\infty \omega(u - s)\varrho(s) ds.$$

Using precise estimates for $\Psi(x, y)$ and $\Phi(x, y)$, we also identify the second term of the asymptotic expansion of $\Theta(x, y, z)$, which is naturally expressed in terms of the partial convolution $\mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v)$ of ϱ' with ω :

$$\mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v) = \int_v^\infty \omega(u - s)\varrho'(s) ds.$$

Theorem 1. *For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain*

$$x \geq 3, \quad y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\}, \quad y \log y \leq z \leq x/y,$$

we have

$$\Theta(x, y, z) = (\varrho(u) + \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v))x - \gamma \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v) \frac{x}{\log y} + O(\mathcal{E}(x, y, z)),$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$, $v = (\log z)/\log y$, γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant, and

$$\mathcal{E}(x, y, z) = \frac{x}{\log y} \left\{ \varrho(u - 1) + \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v + 1)}{\log y} + \frac{\varrho(v)}{\log(v + 1)} \right\}.$$

Similar results have been obtained concomitantly, using a more elaborate approach, by Tenenbaum [8].

The proof of Theorem 1 is given below in Section 4; our principal tools are the estimates of Lemma 4 (Section 2) and Lemma 6 (Section 3). In Section 5, we use the formula of Theorem 1 to give a heuristic prediction for the density of certain integers of cryptographic interest which appear in a work by Menezes [3].

2. Integers Free of Large Prime Factors

In this section, we collect various estimates for the counting function $\Psi(x, y)$ of *y-smooth numbers*:

$$\Psi(x, y) = \#\{n \leq x : P^+(n) \leq y\}.$$

As usual, we denote by $\varrho(u)$ the *Dickman function*; it is continuous at $u = 1$, differentiable for $u > 1$, and it satisfies the differential-difference equation

$$u\varrho'(u) + \varrho(u - 1) = 0 \quad (u > 1), \tag{1}$$

along with the initial condition $\varrho(u) = 1$ ($0 \leq u \leq 1$). It is convenient to define $\varrho(u) = 0$ for all $u < 0$ so that (1) is satisfied for $u \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0, 1\}$, and we also define $\varrho'(u)$ by right-continuity at $u = 0$ and $u = 1$. For a discussion of the analytic properties of $\varrho(u)$, we refer the reader to [6, Chapter III.5].

We need the following well known estimate for $\Psi(x, y)$, which is due to Hildebrand [2] (see also [6, Corollary 9.3, Chapter III.5]):

Lemma 1. *For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain*

$$x \geq 3, \quad x \geq y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\},$$

we have

$$\Psi(x, y) = \varrho(u) x \left\{ 1 + O\left(\frac{\log(u+1)}{\log y}\right) \right\},$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$.

We also need the following extension of Lemma 1, which is a special case of the results of Saias [5]:

Lemma 2. *For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain*

$$x \geq 3, \quad y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\}, \quad x \geq y \log y,$$

the following estimate holds:

$$\Psi(x, y) = \varrho(u) x + (\gamma - 1)\varrho'(u) \frac{x}{\log y} + O\left(\varrho''(u) \frac{x}{\log^2 y}\right),$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$.

The following lemma provides a precise estimate for the sum

$$S(y, z) = \sum_{\substack{d > z \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{1}{d}$$

over a wide range, which is used in the proofs of Lemmas 4 and 6 below. The sum $S(y, z)$ has been previously studied; see, for example, [7].

Lemma 3. For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain

$$y \geq 3, \quad 1 \leq z \leq \exp \exp\{(\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon}\},$$

we have

$$S(y, z) = \tau(v) \log y - \gamma \varrho(v) + O(E(y, z)),$$

where $v = (\log z) / \log y$,

$$\tau(v) = \int_v^\infty \varrho(s) ds,$$

and

$$E(y, z) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v+1)}{\log y} & \text{if } z \geq y \log y; \\ \frac{1}{z} + \frac{\log \log y}{\log y} & \text{if } z < y \log y. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let $Y = y \log y$. First, suppose that $z > Y$, and put $T = \frac{\exp\{(\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon/2}\}}{\log y}$. By partial summation, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} S(y, z) &= \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq y^T \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{1}{d} + S(y, y^T) \\ &= \frac{\Psi(y^T, y)}{y^T} - \frac{\Psi(z, y)}{z} + \log y \int_v^T \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds + S(y, y^T). \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

By Lemma 1, we have the estimate $\frac{\Psi(z, y)}{z} = \varrho(v) + O\left(\frac{\varrho(v) \log(v+1)}{\log y}\right)$.

We now recall that

$$\varrho(w) = \exp(-w \log w + O(w \log \log w)); \tag{3}$$

see [5, Lemma 3(iv)]. Thus, by our choice of T we have

$$\varrho(T) = \exp\left\{- (1 + o(1)) \frac{\exp\{(\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon/2}\}}{(\log y)^{2/5+\varepsilon/2}}\right\}.$$

On the other hand, since $v \leq \log z \leq \exp\{(\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon}\}$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v+1)}{\log y} &= \frac{\exp(-v \log v + O(v \log \log v))}{\log y} \\ &\geq \exp\left\{- (1 + o(1)) \exp\{(\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon}\} (\log y)^{3/5-\varepsilon}\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\Psi(y^T, y)}{y^T} \ll \varrho(T) \ll \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v+1)}{\log y}. \tag{4}$$

The following bound is given in the proof of [7, Corollary 2]:

$$S(y, y^T) = \sum_{\substack{d > y^T \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{1}{d} \ll \varrho(T)e^{\varepsilon T} + y^{-(1-\varepsilon)T},$$

from which we deduce that

$$S(y, y^T) \ll \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v + 1)}{\log y}. \tag{5}$$

To estimate the integral in (2), we apply Lemma 2 and write

$$\int_v^T \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds = I_1 + I_2 + O(I_3),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_v^T \varrho(s) ds = \tau(v) - \tau(T), \\ I_2 &= \frac{(\gamma - 1)}{\log y} \int_v^T \varrho'(s) ds = \frac{(\gamma - 1)(\varrho(T) - \varrho(v))}{\log y}, \\ I_3 &= \frac{1}{\log^2 y} \int_v^T \varrho''(s) ds = \frac{\varrho'(T) - \varrho'(v)}{\log^2 y}. \end{aligned}$$

Using (1) together with [6, Lemma 8.1 and bound (61), Chapter III.5] we see that $|\varrho'(v)| \asymp \varrho(v) \log(v + 1)$. Furthermore, as in our derivation of (4), we see that (3) yields

$$\tau(T) \ll \varrho(T) \ll \frac{\varrho(v) \log(v + 1)}{\log^2 y}.$$

Therefore,

$$\int_v^T \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds = \tau(v) - \frac{(\gamma - 1)\varrho(v)}{\log y} + O\left(\frac{\varrho(v) \log(v + 1)}{\log^2 y}\right). \tag{6}$$

Inserting the estimates (4), (5), and (6) into (2), we obtain the desired estimate when $z > Y$.

Next, suppose that $y \leq z \leq Y$, and put $V = \frac{\log Y}{\log y} = 1 + \frac{\log \log y}{\log y}$. Since $\varrho(s) = 1 - \log s$ for $1 \leq s \leq 2$, we have $1 \geq \varrho(v) \geq \varrho(V) = 1 + O\left(\frac{\log \log y}{\log y}\right)$; therefore,

$$\varrho(v) - \varrho(V) \ll \frac{\log \log y}{\log y}. \tag{7}$$

By partial summation, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} S(y, z) &= \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq Y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{1}{d} + S(y, Y) \\ &= \frac{\Psi(Y, y)}{Y} - \frac{\Psi(z, y)}{z} + \log y \int_v^V \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds + S(y, Y). \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Using Lemma 1 together with (7), it follows that

$$\frac{\Psi(Y, y)}{Y} - \frac{\Psi(z, y)}{z} = \varrho(V) - \varrho(v) + O\left(\frac{1}{\log y}\right) \ll \frac{\log \log y}{\log y}. \tag{9}$$

Applying the estimate from the previous case, we also have

$$S(y, Y) = \tau(V) \log Y - \gamma \varrho(V) + O\left(\frac{1}{\log y}\right). \tag{10}$$

To estimate the integral in (8), we use Lemma 1 again and write

$$\int_v^V \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds = I_4 + O(I_5),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_4 &= \int_v^V \varrho(s) ds = \tau(v) - \tau(V), \\ I_5 &= \frac{1}{\log y} \int_v^V ds = \frac{\log(Y/z)}{\log^2 y} \ll \frac{\log \log y}{\log^2 y}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\int_v^V \frac{\Psi(y^s, y)}{y^s} ds = \tau(v) - \tau(V) + O\left(\frac{\log \log y}{\log^2 y}\right). \tag{11}$$

Inserting the estimates (9), (10) and (11) into (8), and taking into account (7), we obtain the stated estimate for $y \leq z \leq Y$.

Finally, suppose that $1 \leq z < y$. In this case,

$$S(y, z) = \sum_{z < d \leq y} \frac{1}{d} + S(y, y). \tag{12}$$

By partial summation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{z < d \leq y} \frac{1}{d} &= \log y - \log z + O(z^{-1}) = (1 - v) \log y + O(z^{-1}) \\ &= \log y \int_v^1 \varrho(s) ds + O(z^{-1}) = (\tau(v) - \tau(1)) \log y + O(z^{-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Applying the estimate from the previous case, we also have

$$S(y, y) = \tau(1) \log y - \gamma \varrho(1) + O\left(\frac{\log \log y}{\log y}\right).$$

Inserting these estimates into (12), and using the fact that $\varrho(v) = \varrho(1) = 1$, we obtain the desired result. □

Lemma 4. For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain

$$x \geq 3, \quad y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\}, \quad 1 \leq z \leq x/y,$$

we have

$$\sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\varrho(u - u_d)}{d} \ll \mathcal{C}_{\varrho, \varrho}(u, v) \log(u + 1) + \varrho(u - v)\varrho(v) + \varrho(u - 1),$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$, $v = (\log z)/\log y$, $u_d = (\log d)/\log y$ for every integer d in the sum, and

$$\mathcal{C}_{\varrho, \varrho}(u, v) = \int_v^\infty \varrho(u - s)\varrho(s) ds.$$

Proof. By partial summation, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\varrho(u - u_d)}{d} = S(y, x/y) - \varrho(u - v)S(y, z) + \int_v^{u-1} \varrho'(u - s)S(y, y^s) ds.$$

Lemma 3 implies that

$$\begin{aligned} S(y, x/y) &= \tau(u - 1) \log y + O(\varrho(u - 1)), \\ S(y, z) &= \tau(v) \log y + O(\varrho(v)), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\int_v^{u-1} \varrho'(u - s)S(y, y^s) ds = I_1 \log y + O(I_2),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_v^{u-1} \varrho'(u - s)\tau(s) ds = \varrho(u - v)\tau(v) - \tau(u - 1) + \mathcal{C}_{\varrho, \varrho}(u, v), \\ I_2 &= \int_v^{u-1} |\varrho'(u - s)|\varrho(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, using the bound $|\varrho'(t)| \ll \varrho(t) \log(t + 1)$ (for $t > 1$), we see that

$$I_2 \ll \log(u + 1) \int_v^{u-1} \varrho(u - s)\varrho(s) ds \leq \mathcal{C}_{\varrho, \varrho}(u, v) \log(u + 1).$$

Putting everything together, the result follows. □

3. Integers Free of Small Prime Factors

In this section, we collect various estimates for the counting function $\Phi(x, y)$ of *y-rough numbers*:

$$\Phi(x, y) = \#\{n \leq x : P^-(n) > y\}.$$

As usual, we denote by $\omega(u)$ the *Buchstab function*; for $u > 1$, it is the unique continuous solution to the differential-difference equation

$$(u\omega(u))' = \omega(u - 1) \quad (u > 2) \tag{13}$$

with initial condition $u\omega(u) = 1$ ($1 \leq u \leq 2$). It is convenient to define $\omega(u) = 0$ for all $u < 1$ so that (13) is satisfied for $u \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{1, 2\}$, and we also define $\omega'(u)$ by right-continuity at $u = 1$ and $u = 2$. For a discussion of the analytic properties of $\omega(u)$, we refer the reader to [6, Chapter III.6]

The next result follows from [6, Corollary 7.5, Chapter III.6]:

Lemma 5. *For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain*

$$x \geq 3, \quad x \geq y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\},$$

the following estimate holds:

$$\Phi(x, y) = (x\omega(u) - y) \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(1, y)} + O\left(\frac{x\rho(u)}{\log^2 y}\right),$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$, and $\zeta(1, y) = \prod_{p \leq y} (1 - p^{-1})^{-1}$.

Lemma 6. *For fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ and uniformly in the domain*

$$x \geq 3, \quad y \geq \exp\{(\log \log x)^{5/3+\varepsilon}\}, \quad 1 \leq z \leq x/y,$$

we have

$$\sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\omega(u - u_d)}{d} = \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v) \log y - \gamma \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v) + O(E(y, z)),$$

where $u = (\log x)/\log y$, $v = (\log z)/\log y$, $u_d = (\log d)/\log y$ for every integer d in the sum, and $E(y, z)$ is the error term of Lemma 3.

Proof. By partial summation, it follows that

$$\sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\omega(u - u_d)}{d} = S(y, x/y) - \omega(u - v)S(y, z) + \int_v^{u-1} \omega'(u - s)S(y, y^s) ds.$$

By Lemma 3 we have the estimates $S(y, x/y) = \tau(u - 1) \log y - \gamma \varrho(u - 1) + O(E(y, x/y))$ and $S(y, z) = \tau(v) \log y - \gamma \varrho(v) + O(E(y, z))$. Also,

$$\int_v^{u-1} \omega'(u - s) S(y, y^s) ds = I_1 \log y - \gamma I_2 + O(I_3),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_v^{u-1} \omega'(u - s) \tau(s) ds = \omega(u - v) \tau(v) - \tau(u - 1) + \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v), \\ I_2 &= \int_v^{u-1} \omega'(u - s) \varrho(s) ds = \omega(u - v) \varrho(v) - \varrho(u - 1) + \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v), \\ I_3 &= \frac{1}{\log y} \int_v^{u-1} |\omega'(u - s)| E(y, y^s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Putting everything together, we see that the stated estimate follows from the bound

$$E(y, x/y) + \omega(u - v) E(y, z) + I_3 \ll E(y, z). \tag{14}$$

To prove this, observe that $E(y, z_1) \ll E(y, z_2)$ holds for all $z_1 \geq z_2 \geq 1$. Therefore, $E(y, x/y) \ll E(y, z)$, and

$$I_3 \ll \frac{E(y, z)}{\log y} \int_v^{u-1} |\omega'(u - s)| ds \ll \frac{E(y, z)}{\log y}.$$

Taking into account the fact that $\omega(u - v) \asymp 1$, we derive (14), completing the proof. \square

4. Proof of Theorem 1

For fixed y , every positive integer n can be uniquely decomposed as a product $n = de$, where $P^+(d) \leq y$ and $P^-(e) > y$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta(x, y, z) &= \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \sum_{\substack{e \leq x/d \\ P^-(e) > y}} 1 = \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \Phi(x/d, y) \\ &= \Psi(x, y) - \Psi(x/y, y) + \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \Phi(x/d, y). \end{aligned}$$

Using Lemma 1, it follows that $\Psi(x, y) - \Psi(x/y, y) = \varrho(u)x + O\left(\frac{\varrho(u-1)x}{\log y}\right)$. By Lemma 5, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \Phi(x/d, y) &= \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \left\{ \left(\frac{x\omega(u-u_d)}{d} - y \right) \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(1, y)} + O\left(\frac{x\varrho(u-u_d)}{d \log^2 y}\right) \right\} \\ &= \frac{e^\gamma x}{\zeta(1, y)} \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\omega(u-u_d)}{d} - \frac{e^\gamma y}{\zeta(1, y)} \{ \Psi(x/y, y) - \Psi(z, y) \} \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x}{\log^2 y} \sum_{\substack{z < d \leq x/y \\ P^+(d) \leq y}} \frac{\varrho(u-u_d)}{d}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Applying Lemma 1 again, we have $-\frac{e^\gamma y}{\zeta(1, y)} \{ \Psi(x/y, y) - \Psi(z, y) \} \ll \frac{\varrho(u-1)x}{\log y}$. Inserting the estimates of Lemmas 4 and 6 into (15), and making use of the trivial estimate

$$\mathcal{C}_{\varrho, \varrho}(u, v) \log(u+1) \ll \log y \int_v^\infty \varrho(s) ds \ll \frac{\varrho(v) \log y}{\log(v+1)}.$$

it is easy to see that

$$\Theta(x, y, z) = \left(\varrho(u) + \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v) \frac{e^\gamma \log y}{\zeta(1, y)} \right) x - \gamma \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v) \frac{e^\gamma x}{\zeta(1, y)} + O(\mathcal{E}(x, y, z)).$$

To complete to proof, we use the estimate (see Vinogradov [9]):

$$\zeta(1, y) = e^\gamma \log y (1 + \exp\{-c(\log y)^{3/5}\}),$$

which holds for some absolute constant $c > 0$, together with the trivial estimate

$$\max\{\mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(u, v), \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(u, v)\} \ll \int_v^\infty \varrho(s) ds \ll \frac{\varrho(v)}{\log(v+1)}.$$

5. Cryptographic Applications

Suppose that two primes p and q are selected for use in the *Digital Signature Algorithm* (see, for example, [4]) using the following standard method:

- Select a random m -bit prime q ;
- Randomly generate k -bit integers n until a prime $p = 2nq + 1$ is reached.

The *large subgroup attack* described in [3, Section 3.2.3] leads one naturally to consider the following question: What is the probability $\eta(k, \ell, m)$ that n has a divisor $s > q$ which is 2^ℓ -smooth?

It is natural to expect that the proportion of those integers in the set $\{2^{k-1} \leq n < 2^k\}$ having a large smooth divisor should be roughly the same as the proportion of integers in

$$\{2^{k-1} \leq n < 2^k : n = (p - 1)/(2q) \text{ for some prime } p \equiv 1 \pmod{2q}\}$$

having a large smooth divisor. Accordingly, we expect that the probability $\eta(k, \ell, m)$ is reasonably close to

$$\frac{\Theta(2^k, 2^\ell, 2^m) - \Theta(2^{k-1}, 2^\ell, 2^m)}{2^{k-1}}.$$

Theorem 1 then suggests that $\eta(k, \ell, m) \approx 2\wp(k, \ell, m) - \wp(k - 1, \ell, m)$, where

$$\wp(k, \ell, m) = \varrho(k/\ell) + \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho}(k/\ell, m/\ell) - \frac{\gamma \mathcal{C}_{\omega, \varrho'}(k/\ell, m/\ell)}{\ell \log 2}.$$

In particular, the most interesting choice of parameters at the present time is $k = 863$, $\ell = 80$, and $m = 160$ (which produce a 1024-bit prime p); we expect $\eta(863, 80, 160) \approx 0.09576$.

Acknowledgements. The authors would like to thank Alfred Menezes for bringing to our attention the cryptographic applications which initially motivated our work. We also thank Gérald Tenenbaum for pointing out a mistake in the original manuscript, and for many subsequent discussions. This work was started during a visit by W. B. to Macquarie University; the support and hospitality of this institution are gratefully acknowledged. During the preparation of this paper, I. S. was supported in part by ARC grant DP0556431.

References

- [1] R. R. Hall and G. Tenenbaum, *Divisors*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1988.
- [2] A. Hildebrand, ‘On the number of positive integers $\leq x$ and free of prime factors $> y$,’ *J. Number Theory* **22**, (1986), no. 3, 289–307.
- [3] A. J. Menezes, ‘Another look at HMQV’, *Cryptology ePrint Archive, Report 2005/205*, 2005, 1–15.
- [4] A. J. Menezes, P. C. van Oorschot and S. A. Vanstone, *Handbook of applied cryptography*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1996.
- [5] É. Saias, ‘Sur le nombre des entiers sans grand facteur premier,’ (French) *J. Number Theory* **32** (1989), no. 1, 78–99.
- [6] G. Tenenbaum, *Introduction to analytic and probabilistic number theory*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1995.
- [7] G. Tenenbaum, *Crible d’Ératosthène et modèle de Kubilius*, Number theory in progress, Vol. 2 (Zakopane-Kościelisko, 1997), de Gruyter, Berlin, 1999, 1099–1129.
- [8] G. Tenenbaum, *Integers with a large friable component*, Preprint, 2006.
- [9] A. I. Vinogradov, ‘On the remainder in Merten’s formula,’ (Russian) *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR* **148** (1963), 262–263.